

A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE DEVELOPMENT THROUGH FUNDAMENTAL HUMAN NEEDS: RESPECT AND RECOGNITION AT WORKPLACE

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Cite This Article: Yashashwi. A. Ail, "A Study on Employee Development Through Fundamental Human Needs: Respect and Recognition at Workplace", International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology, Page Number 65-68, Volume 1, Issue 1, 2016

Abstract:

In the modern competitive world, the greatest asset of any organization is its "Employees". Employee is an individual who delivers his service to the workplace where he is being employed. Today, there is a new way for reaping the best of the organization through "Employee Development". Nurturing the growth of employees is known to be Employee Development which takes place through a number of training, motivational and developmental activities. Motivational Factors like Promotions, Appraisals, Recognition, Respect and Rewards are the few to enhance the Employee skills and abilities. Sir Abraham .H. Maslow has propounded a Motivational Need Hierarchy Theory which throws light on Employee motivational factors. Benefits of Employee Development is procured by both employee as well as the organization where he renders his service. The study is mainly centered on "Employee Development through the fundamental human needs: Recognition and Respect at workplace" with special reference to Employee Development at Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Pandeshwar, Mangalore. The study discovers the fundamental human needs- Recognition and Respect gained by the employees of the above said Institution which lands on Employee Development.

Index Terms: Recognition, Respect & Employee Development

1. Introduction:

One of the major challenges of modern competitive organizations and institutions is "Employee Development" where "Employees" are the greatest Asset and backbone of an organization so called as the Human Resource. It is the very need of every organization to value, nurture and retain their employees with them, which is beneficial for organizations success. In the beginning an employee is like a Flower Bud which has to be given proper care and support through developmental activities and him to blossom like a Flower. Development can take place through a number of training, motivation and developmental activities. Motivational factors like Promotions, Appraisals, Recognition, Respect and Rewards are the few to enhance the employee skills and activities. Without employees even a powerful machinery or technology cannot function. So employees need to spend some time and resource in developing their employees. Benefits of employee development is reaped by both employee as well as the organization where he renders his service. It is an initiative which can be jointly taken up by an employee as well as the employer in order to boost the existing skills and knowledge sets of an individual. Employee development is the result of various motivational factors in which "Respect and Recognition" are considered to be the fundamental human needs in a workplace. This study throws light on the Respect and Recognition effect on employee development.

2. Objective of the Study:

To know how the employee development takes place in the institution. To gather information on how effective is the employee development program. To analyze how development takes place through fundamental human needs: Respect and Recognition. Discovers the respect and recognition effect on employee development.

Employee: Employee is an individual who delivers his service to the workplace where he is being employed. Employees who work in an organization by giving his/her heart and soul to his/her duties assigned also expects something in return from his/her employer or the organization. Developmental activities by the employer can make the employee cherish with higher skills and abilities with career growth.

Employee Development: Individual in any organization or institution forms an important resource which need to be nurtured and developed. Employee is the most valuable asset and backbone of any organization. Employee development is a joint action or initiative by employee as well as by his/her employer to enhance the knowledge and abilities of an employee and help him/her to survive the competition. It helps an employee to become a valuable resource which benefits the organization as well as leads to his/her personality development. It leads to professional growth and personal growth.

5 Keys to Employee Development:

- ✓ Coaching
- ✓ Mentoring
- ✓ Counseling
- ✓ Teaching
- ✓ Training

Employee Development Activities:

- ✓ Motivate employees to participate in ED programmes.
- ✓ Make employees to believe in ED programmes.
- ✓ Give learning opportunities to employees.
- ✓ Create a positive work environment.
- ✓ Give supportive feedback and performance appraisals.
- ✓ Provide guidelines to employees on what he is supposed to do in organization.

3. Fundamental Human Needs: Respect & Recognition:

Respect: Respect is a feeling of admiration towards someone or something because of their skills, character, position or achievements. Every individual wants to be respected from others, which is a motivational factor. It has a positive impact on an individual, his work and his relationships. Respect is commonly compared with Oxygen which helps an e out of the work. There is a famous quote which says Give Respect and Take Respect. Every individual employee needs to be respected which leads him to employee development. The term respect itself says what an employee needs in his workplace.

- R – Recognition
- E – Exciting Task
- S – Security of Job
- P – Pay
- E – Education
- C – Career Development
- T – Truthfulness

There is no particular way to respect. Respect itself is the way. When the employees are treated well with due respect and regards by the employer, it makes them feel happy and contented to their workplace. This in one way helps to retain the employees by creating good image about the employer and the organization, where lack of respect hurts an employee resulting in poor performance or involvement in organizational activities.

7 Ways to Master Respect Effect: There are certain ways which need to be practiced by the employer and their colleagues who work together as a team.

Self Respect - First and we should be kind and caring to ourselves.

Value People - show certain human values to your workers or colleagues.

Be Empathic - we should leave back our ego behind by seeing the world from others perspective

Measure the Cost of Disrespect – Respect has a positive effect where as disrespect has a negative effect on an individual

Everyone Should be Aware of Their Behavior – For example, when we crack jokes with an intention to offend the other person, we should be aware that he/she is being hurt.

Employees Look for:

- ✓ Stability in work
- ✓ Good compensation / remuneration
- ✓ Due respect
- ✓ Health benefits
- ✓ Work-life balance

These are the fundamental human needs of an employee .when these are satisfied it leads to Employee development which can be done by an organization / employer without incurring much cost and time on ED Programmes.

Employers Duty Towards Respect Effect:

- ✓ Let your employees know that you care about them.
- ✓ Do not raise your voice to employees.
- ✓ Show them the right path.
- ✓ Never criticize them in front of others/ peers.
- ✓ Listen to your employees
- ✓ Learn the key strength of your employees
- ✓ Recommend the training facilities for employees who need it
- ✓ Have a regular communication with your employees
- ✓ Keep them informed and up –to- date
- ✓ Encourage them.
- ✓ Find out the motivational factors which develops an employee
- ✓ Assign more challenging tasks and projects
- ✓ Employees performance should be duely rewarded
- ✓ Have faith and trust on employees.

Recognition: Abraham H Maslow clearly states in his Need Hierarchy Theory that every individual need to be recognized by others, which creates a positive impact on himself. Similarly, employee recognition must be a

common practice in every organization/institutions. Employee need to be recognized for both individual achievements and group achievements. Recognition is thanking employees and acknowledging their efforts and contributions there must be sincere and heartfelt employee recognition.

Importance of Recognition:

- ✓ Improves employee morality
- ✓ Builds a supportive work environment
- ✓ Helps in employee retention
- ✓ Increases employee motivation
- ✓ Employees develop a sense of belongingness
- ✓ Lets employee to know that their work is being appreciated and valued.

Recognition Ideas for Employers:

- ✓ Thank the person by name
- ✓ Say a single “Hello” at the start of the day and “Bye” at the end of the day, makes the employee recognized.
- ✓ Explain about their good behavior.
- ✓ Appreciate your staff in management meetings and special events.
- ✓ Reward their achievements.

4. Area of Study:

This study is done at Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Pandeshwar, Mangalore (SIMS) where the concepts of Respect and Recognition at workplace as a key factor in employee development are highlighted with reference to only the Faculty members of Department of Commerce and Management. Here Employee Development takes place in different ways:

5. Methods of Employee Development at SIMS:

- ✓ Organizes FDP – Faculty Development Programmes every Saturdays
- ✓ Encourages employees to participate in Seminars and conferences
- ✓ Creates platform to learn new things.
- ✓ Provides additional responsibilities and tasks
- ✓ Sets targets for achievements
- ✓ Carries performance appraisals

6. Role of Principal in Employee Development:

- Principal of SIMS is playing active role in Employee Development in following ways:
- ✓ Encourages and motivates every faculty members and other staffs of the institution.
 - ✓ Assigns various challenging tasks to every faculties during seminars, conferences and other college activities.
 - ✓ Faculties are provided with technological support which helps in improving their technological skills.
 - ✓ Holds staff meetings oftenly to motivate his faculty members.
 - ✓ Sets the targets for the duties assigned.
 - ✓ Encourages to attend seminars and workshops which helps in employee development.
 - ✓ Supports every faculties in doing Research.
 - ✓ Successfully organizes 4 conferences in a academic year where all the faculties get an opportunity to present their research papers.
 - ✓ Encourages employees to register for online or distance learning courses.

7. Respect at SIMS:

- ✓ All the faculty members are treated equally in the institution.
- ✓ Every faculty gets the respect with greetings right from the entrance of the college gate by the Security Guard, which makes the day start with a smile on everyone’s face.
- ✓ Respect is equally expressed by office staffs and every students of the institution.
- ✓ Every faculty gets due respect from the Principal.
- ✓ Opinions and ideas of each faculty is being considered with due respect.
- ✓ Names of every faculties are addressed with the word sir/ madam which itself is a symbol of respect.

8. Recognition at SIMS:

- ✓ Every individual employee is being recognized in a positive way.
- ✓ Recognition is provided in every staff meetings.
- ✓ By assigning different duties every faculty is recognized.
- ✓ New faculties are introduced to all the members of the institution.
- ✓ The achievements of each faculty is appreciated and recognized.
- ✓ Best Teachers Award is given to those faculties who excel in their teachings and developmental activities.
- ✓ Recognition is also carried through Academic Result Analysis.
- ✓ The good achievements of each individual is recognized and appreciated.

- ✓ Employees recognized are given with suitable Promotions.

9. Conclusion:

This study on Employee Development with respect and recognition proves good to the above said institution with reference to the Faculty members of Department of commerce and management. The study reveals the culture of respect in the institution and the supportive role of Principal towards Employee Development. The institution observes Employee Development through fundamental human needs: Respect and Recognition.

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